

M3.1 Strategy for inclusion of credit for research assets decided

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Milestone M3.1, "*Strategy for inclusion of credit for research assets decided*," focuses on developing a strategy to credit scientists for contributions beyond traditional publications. It builds on existing platforms like APICURON, BIP! Scholar, and ORCID to propose an ecosystem that ensures scientists receive appropriate credit and visibility, recognizing their contributions to scientific artifacts beyond traditional publications such as research data, software, tools, workflows, and training.

Introduction

In today's research landscape, the variety of research outputs generated by researchers is broader than ever. While traditional frameworks are primarily focused on scholarly publications, other research assets are now considered vital for scientific progress. Examples of these assets include:

- *Software tools/workflows*: any set of reusable software contributing to research and Open Science.
- *Research infrastructure*: any system and platform essential for supporting data storage and collaborative research.
- *Standards and protocols*: guidelines ensuring consistency, interoperability, and reproducibility in research.
- *Training materials/courses*: educational resources providing researchers with essential skills and knowledge.
- *Datasets and data curation*: organized and curated collections of scientific data.

To reflect the diverse contributions in research, crediting and recognition systems must evolve to become more inclusive. Well-established initiatives, including Hidden REF and CoARA, aim to address relevant challenges providing valuable recommendations towards a more responsible and inclusive researcher crediting and recognition framework. From a

practical perspective, a clearly defined strategy that establishes the infrastructure and metadata required for appropriate acknowledgment of these contributions is required.

General Strategy

Implementing a general and inclusive strategy for recognizing researcher contributions requires the establishment of an ecosystem of platforms (see *Figure 1*) as outlined below:

- **Research Publishing Platforms:** these platforms collect, maintain, and publish research assets submitted by researchers. They also gather basic metadata related to the assets. Indicative examples of such platforms include:
 - Research Asset Repositories (e.g., source code repositories, preprint repositories)
 - Research Journals & Publishers
 - Research Activity Registries
- **Researcher PID Providers:** these services provide researchers with persistent identifiers (PIDs), which can be used during the submission of research assets to ensure unique identification. Publishing platforms incorporate researcher PIDs in the assets' metadata, enabling aggregators and recognition platforms to appropriately recognize a researcher's activities and contributions.
- **Research Metadata Enrichment Services:** these services enrich the basic research asset metadata provided by the Research Publishing Platforms. The enrichments could be automatically generated (AI/ML) or curated by humans. Indicative examples include research performance indicators, contribution roles (e.g., CRedit-based), topics, and more.
- **Research Metadata Aggregators:** these services collect, merge, clean, and homogenize research-related metadata from various sources, providing end users with easy access to the aggregated information. Indicative examples of such services include:
 - Contribution Trackers (collecting asset tracks for researchers)
 - Scientific Knowledge Graphs (universal aggregators that collect research metadata in a standardized format for analysis and other purposes)
- **Researcher Contribution Platforms:** these platforms collect research-related information from Research Metadata Aggregators to provide analytics, visualizations, gamification features (e.g., badges, leaderboards), and profiles that help recognise and credit researchers' work. Indicative examples of such platforms include:
 - Reward and Gamification Platforms (focused on rewarding and incentivizing research work).

- Academic Profile Platforms (focused on fully recognizing and sharing researchers' contributions).

Figure 1. Bird's eye view of the ecosystem for crediting shows the interactions among the various types of components.

Furthermore, the outlined ecosystem reduces researchers' interaction with multiple entities. As shown in (Figure 2), the researcher only needs to interact with two key architecture components, while the other components operate autonomously in the process of crediting and recognition without requiring the researcher's direct involvement. In the future, this ecosystem could be further expanded to consider networks of researchers (i.e. communities).

Figure 2. Representation of the Researcher's possible interaction with the crediting ecosystem.

Strategy Implementation: Leveraging Key Platforms

The previous section introduced a high-level architecture for an ecosystem of federated platforms, which will be leveraged to implement a strategy for recognizing research assets.

To operationalize this strategy effectively, we plan to leverage, customize, and build upon an array of existing platforms aligned with the identified roles (see *Figure 3*). Below, we outline how these platforms will empower scientists to receive credit for research assets and activities beyond traditional publications.

- **Researcher PID Providers:** ORCID¹ offers a free, unique, persistent identifier (PID) for researchers that will be utilized to ensure the consistent and accurate tracking of researchers' contributions across various platforms.
- **Research Metadata Aggregators & Researcher Contribution Platforms:** APICURON² will function as a central aggregator and contribution platform, compiling and displaying research contributions to comprehensively represent researchers' work and offer rewarding and gamification systems. Metadata from other aggregators (e.g., the OpenAIRE Graph³) will be used supplementarily. Finally, BIP! Scholar⁴ will

¹ORCID: <https://orcid.org/>

²APICURON: <https://apicuron.org/>

³OpenAIRE Graph: <https://graph.openaire.eu/>

⁴BIP! Scholar: <https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/scholar>

be a central service to host academic profiles based on templates emphasizing research software-related activities.

- **Research Metadata Enrichment Services:** platforms such as BIP! Scholar and the OpenEBench Observatory⁵ will enrich the metadata associated with research assets with contextual information and indicators that can be used to highlight different aspects of the researcher's research career.
- **Research Publishing Platforms:** established platforms, such as EMBL-EBI⁶, Zenodo⁷, WorkflowHub⁸, bio.tools⁹, DisProt¹⁰, and ELIXIR TeSS¹¹ will serve as repositories for research assets, feeding into the broader ecosystem that supports recognition and crediting mechanisms. The specific array of platforms to be used will be decided at a later stage (D3.1 will include the relevant details).

Figure 3. The role of platforms mentioned in the proposal in relation to their respective components.

It is important to highlight that STEERS is not currently focused on providing a detailed implementation plan for the proposed ecosystem. The current priority is to establish a high-level architecture, with specific implementation details to be outlined in Deliverable D3.1, titled “*Report on Credit and Software Management Plan Implementation*”.

Key platforms that will significantly contribute to the crediting ecosystem are summarized in the following paragraphs.

⁵ OpenEBench Observatory: <https://openebench.bsc.es/observatory/Data/>

⁶ EMBL-EBI <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/>

⁷ Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/>

⁸ WorkflowHub <https://workflowhub.eu/>

⁹ bio.tools <https://bio.tools/>

¹⁰ DisProt <https://disprot.org/>

¹¹ ELIXIR TeSS <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>

APICURON

APICURON is a comprehensive database specifically developed to recognize and attribute credit to biocurators by meticulously tracking and aggregating their contributions across various knowledge bases. The foundation of APICURON lies in its ability to monitor activities performed on digital objects accessible on the web, including datasets, proteins, and other related entities. While its current emphasis is on tracking curation activities, APICURON carries the potential to expand its scope to encompass a broader range of research assets generated across diverse platforms, thereby enhancing its utility and impact within the scientific community.

BIP! Scholar

BIP! Scholar is a platform that allows researchers to create profiles representing their research activities, enrich them with contextual information, and highlight different aspects of their research careers. The main objective of the platform is to offer profiles that cover a wide range of research activities, going beyond scientific publications. The platform leverages data from scholarly knowledge graphs (OpenAIRE Graph, Crossref, OpenCitations) and ORCID to display custom reports containing lists of contributions and a variety of indicators that capture different aspects of the researchers' performance (e.g., productivity, impact, career stage), while considering their different roles in the respective works (according to the CRediT taxonomy). The platform also supports multiple ways to present (and download) researcher profiles, offering both traditional and innovative templates (e.g., narrative CV templates) aimed at being more responsible and inclusive. Finally, BIP! Scholar profiles can be dynamically tailored by the viewer to facilitate the examination of a researcher's career according to specific topics, roles or types of activity that may be of interest.

OpenEBench

OpenEBench is a benchmarking infrastructure platform for bioinformatics' methods, tools, and web services. Part of the ELIXIR Tools platform and developed by the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) in collaboration with partners within ELIXIR and beyond. The platform's main objective is to allow researchers to publicly benchmark their software (methods or tools), aiming to monitor and improve software quality in life sciences. The platform serves as a repository for software benchmarks, which are associated with the authors of the benchmarking challenge and the authors of each participating software in each challenge, making OpenEBench a repository for software benchmarks that can represent research assets associated with various contributors.

Bio.tools

Bio.tools is a registry of software and databases that facilitates research from across biological and biomedical science to find, understand, utilize, and cite the resources they

need in their day-to-day work. The platform serves as a research publishing platform, allowing researchers to publish their research assets (tools and databases), while also providing a research metadata enrichment service. This service encourages the inclusion of necessary metadata for the published tools, which is subsequently made publicly available.

Conclusion

The strategy presented above outlines a comprehensive approach to recognizing and crediting a wide array of research assets, in alignment with the principles of open science. By leveraging well-established platforms such as APICURON, ORCID, and BIP! Scholar within an ecosystem of interconnected tools, this strategy ensures that researchers receive appropriate acknowledgment for their diverse contributions beyond traditional publications. It addresses the increasing demand for inclusive crediting systems that accurately reflect the landscape of scientific outputs, fostering greater recognition for all aspects of research. To further support recognition and research assessment and to emphasize the significance of synergy among various other European initiatives, this report also reflects our interpretation of the preliminary discussions surrounding the EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Group⁵ (“Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upscaling”) and the Working Group Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment (OI4RRA) of CoARA. It underscores the importance of ensuring alignment both now and in future endeavors.

